

Power Relations: World „Cultural Centres” in Romanian Novels

Romanian novels advance, by means of their adherence to European cultural spaces, an interactive prose map, gravitating around a series of power centres, which magnetically align the narration and, implicitly, the characters' journeys. In spite of their belonging to a "periphery" culture, Romanian literary texts employ, by means of their numerous references to European capitals, a real connection between cultural spaces.

The main objective of the present study is to prove the existence of a network of geographic landmarks reconstituted by resorting to Romanian novels from the first half of the 20th century and the existence of various „cultural centres” inserted into the fictional framework. The main methods of analysis are geocriticism and literary cartography. We will make use of the idea of „cultural centres” which is theorized and analysed on the basis of maps in Herve They's appendix to *The Main Locations of Latin American Literature*, but also in *Introducing Comparative Literature: New Trends and Applications* written by César Domínguez, Haun Saussy, Darío Villanueva, while the manner of usage is connected to the points of influence of „Literary/Cultural Capitals” on Romanian Literary spaces, as they are presented in some Romanian novels, published between 1900-1950.

The study poses the problem of relating to big European capitals, characterised simultaneously by attracting and repelling forces, fascination and rejection, for the character coming from the Romanian space. In order to prove this, we will resort to the novels of a writer who has been compared to Virginia Woolf, because of her narrative innovation: Hortensia Papadat-Bengescu (1876-1955). Throughout the narration in her stream-novel dedicated to the Hallipas, „cultural centres” such as Austria appear by means of the capital Vienna as a centre of the aristocracy as well as a medical centre, Poland by means of Warsaw, as the place of a „grand export endeavour”, France by means of references to the characters' studies and Switzerland by means of the presentation of therapy centres preferred by the Romanian aristocracy. Lenora, one of the female characters in *Dishevelled Virgins* travels to Vienna, where her daughter Coca-Aimee is studying, but also for a medical check-up. The author interferes with a somewhat subjective remark: „Hypochondria typical of spoiled women”, adding: „It was mere caprice that had brought her to Vienna instead of Bucharest” (69). Such examples prove the manner in which this closeness to cultural spaces abroad functions and the justification of access to them.

With Liviu Rebreanu (1885-1944), the second author discussed in this study, Budapest and Vienna are university centres where the character Apostol Bologa (from the novel *Forest of the Hanged* 1922) studies and travels. He enrolls in a "students' college" in Budapest, in order to complete his studies. He integrates into the new space, by learning Hungarian and German within a few months. The fascination with the matrix cultural centre is doubled by a permanent return to the past, with the capital city simultaneously attracting and repelling him: „Life in the capital however he abhorred. The noisy streets, the people's selfishness, the mechanisation of life, upset him” (25). He notices however that the hills around Buda resemble the ones in his native village in Transylvania, Parva. Attraction and repulsion, both generated by the same cultural centre referred to before.

The analysis of these spatial details and the identification of geographic coordinates existing within the narration are able to offer a new perspective, integrating Romanian literature into the larger context of WorldLiterature.

Bako, Alina. "Geocritical Readings of Romanian Literature: Maps and Cartography in Rebreanu's Canonical Fiction." *The Slavonic and East European Review*, vol. 99, no. 2, 2021, pp. 230–255. JSTOR, www.jstor.org/stable/10.5699/slaveasteurorev2.99.2.0230. Accessed 18 Aug. 2021.

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